

UKCoR RDA Day 2026: The Language of RDA

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Useful Links

RDA Toolkit: <https://access.rdatoolkit.org>

Thanks to James Hennelly, Director of ALA Digital Reference, if you do not have institutional / personal access, you can use this login until 9 April:

User Name: UKCoR

Password: RDAday

LRM: <https://repository.ifla.org/handle/20.500.14598/40.2> (Summary of Changes:

<https://repository.ifla.org/handle/20.500.14598/40.2> ; LRM 2017:

<https://repository.ifla.org/handle/20.500.14598/40>)

ISBD: <https://www.ifla.org/g/isbd-rg/isbd-editions/>

ISBD for Manifestations (ISBDM): <https://www.iflastandards.info/ISBDM/>

MARC Manual: <https://www.loc.gov/marc/>

Library of Congress Authorities: <https://authorities.loc.gov/>

DCRMR - <https://rbms.info/dcrm/dcrm/>

RBMS Controlled Vocabulary - <https://id.loc.gov/vocabulary/rbmsev.html>

The activities we are doing today are based on a confidence-building approach, stemming from the viewpoint I outlined in ‘Xenoglossophobia: taming the fear of all the jargon’, *Catalogue & Index* 213 (2025): 10-17, <https://journals.cilip.org.uk/catalogue-and-index/article/view/845>

Toolkit Sections On Which We Are Focusing Today

Guidance > [Introduction to RDA](#)

Guidance > [Terminology](#)

Resources > [Glossary](#) (and [RDA Registry | Vocabularies](#) which is Open Access)

Policies > [British Library Policy Statements](#)

Activities

1. Buzzword Bingo

Choose one of the following words / phrases and keep a tally of how many times it is used. The winner is the one whose buzzword is used most frequently.

AGGREGATE

AACR2

ANGLO-AMERICAN

BLPS

COMMUNITY RESOURCES

COUNTDOWN CLOCK

DIACHRONIC

ELEMENT(S)

ENTITY / ENTITIES EXTENT

INTERNATIONALIZATION

LEGACY

LRM

MANIFESTATION(S)

OFFICIAL RDA

ORIGINAL RDA

PRERECORDING

RECORDING

SOFT-DEPRECATED

STRUCTURED

TRANSCRIPTION

UNSTRUCTURED

WORK(S)

2. Jargon Soup

- (a) How many RDA terms do you know already? (Keep the number to yourself for silent smugness later).
- (b) Check the meanings against the Glossary.
- (c) Find the meanings of the terms you do not know

3. ARCItypes

I will explain when we get there.

Words of the (RDA) Day

COUNTDOWN CLOCK

GUIDANCE

ELEMENT(S)

ENTITY /ENTITIES

AGENTS

POLICY STATEMENTS

APPLICATION PROFILE

SES

EXTENT

SOFT-DEPRECATED

LEAF / LEAVES

STATEMENT(S) OF RESPONSIBILITY

MAIN ENTRY

ADDED ENTRY

ACCESS POINT(S)

UNIFORM TITLE

Bonus Buzzwords

NOMEN

NEOLOGISM